

1 **Rbm6 is selectively activated during the first cell division of the human embryo.**

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6 We studied gene expression in the human embryo immediately after fertilization and zygotic activation and
7 at the first cell division from 1-cell to 2-cell stage. We describe here discovery/identification of Rbm6 as a
8 zygotic cell factor required or important during the first cell division of the fertilized human embryo.

9 Citations

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